

The Influence of Incentive Factors, Work Facilities and Leadership Style on Employee Performance at Pt. United Motors Center Jember Branch

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Abstract: Companies as one of the important components in economic activity are certainly not spared from the overall national economic conditions. National economic problems that arise raise problems in the company's internal environment. The increase in the cost of living due to the increase or instability of some prices of basic necessities has an impact on society in general, including employees who work for companies. Declining company profits due to the impact of economic conditions also had an impact on the company's ability to provide the expected facilities. This is a small example of problems that arise systemically from national economic conditions. Under these conditions Human resources are still the focus and foundation for companies to survive. Optimal performance of each employee is the foundation of the company to always go through the difficult times that are being faced and will be faced. Optimal performance of employees is influenced by several factors of incentives, work facilities and leadership style are several important factors to improve employee performance in a company. PT. UMC (United Motors Center) as a Suzuki Main Dealer for the East Java region, and has many branches in the East Java region, one of which is the Jember branch, of course, experiences similar problems in the dynamics of the company. It is hoped that the results of research conducted by researchers will be able to benefit companies, especially in making strategic decisions to improve employee performance where the final output is an increase in overall company performance.

Keyword:- Influence Factors Incentives, Work Facilities And Leadership Style.

I. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia's post-covid 19 economic condition is facing a new episode. Data from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) shows that Indonesia experienced a contraction in economic growth in 2020 of -2.07 percent. This has caused the Indonesian economy to experience deflation or a drastic decline in 2020 because economic development in Indonesia has an unstable movement. Several policies issued by the government to stabilize the condition of the national economy. The policies issued by the Central Government are fiscal policy and monetary policy. This policy is realized together with the Regional Government and the community because both of them have a strategic role in carrying out the policy.

Companies as one of the important components in economic activity are certainly not spared from the overall national economic conditions. National economic problems that arise raise problems in the company's internal environment. The increase in the cost of living due to the increase or instability of some prices of basic necessities has an impact on society in general, including employees who work for companies. Declining company profits due to the impact of economic conditions also had an impact on the company's ability to provide the expected facilities. This is a small example of problems that arise systemically from national economic conditions.

Under these conditions Human resources are still the focus and foundation for companies to survive. Optimal performance of each employee is the foundation of the company to always go through the difficult times that are currently and will be faced. Optimal performance of employees is influenced by several factors. An important factor that employees pay attention to in the company is incentives. Providing incentives is one of the main things that must be considered by the company. The enthusiasm of employees can also be caused by the size of the incentives received. If employees do not get incentives that are in accordance with the amount of sacrifice at work, then these employees tend to be lazy to work and not enthusiastic, which in the end they work as they please without high motivation. With the provision of appropriate incentives organizational work processes can run according to organizational goals. Incentives have two aspects of interest, namely for the company and for the employees themselves. For companies, incentives are implemented with the intention of retaining high performing employees and motivating underachieving employees. For employees, besides encouraging them to work harder, giving incentives is intended to improve employee welfare. If the employee's welfare is fulfilled, the employee will be better off and it is hoped that it will also affect his work performance. Incentives are implemented with the intention of retaining high performing employees and motivating underachieving employees. For employees, besides encouraging them to work harder, giving incentives is intended to improve employee welfare. If the employee's welfare is fulfilled, the employee will be better off and it is hoped that it will also affect his work performance. Incentives are implemented with the intention of retaining high performing employees and motivating underachieving employees. For employees, besides encouraging them to work harder, giving incentives is intended to improve employee welfare. If the employee's welfare is fulfilled, the employee will be better off and it is hoped that it will also affect his work performance.

In order to motivate employee performance, the company also provides and provides work facilities. Work facilities are one of the incentives for someone to carry out an activity in order to get the best results. Therefore, do not be surprised if a company has adequate work facilities to make it easier for employees to complete their work on time and provide the best for the company and vice versa. In addition to incentives and work facilities, there are other factors that can improve performance employees is a leadership style. The leadership style factor can be a motor and encouragement employee at work. Leader's ability to manage employee will make the situation and work environment very comfortable and enjoyable. PT United Motors Centre Company was founded in Surabaya in 1952. This multinational automotive company is located at Jalan Jendral Basuki Rahmat no.14. In line with the Government Regulation concerning the use of the name of a limited liability company, since 2001 PT United Motors Centre Company has changed its name to PT United Motors Centre. Currently PT. UMC was entrusted with being the Main Dealer for Suzuki for the East Java region, and has 16 branch offices in the East Java region, one of which is in the Jember branch.

PT. UMC Jember Branch is located at Jalan Hayam Wuruk no. 2 jember, is a 3S dealer (sales, service, spare parts). Has work areas in the Jember, Lumajang, Bondowoso, Situbondo and Banyuwangi regions. PT. UMC Jember Branch has 44 employees with the following description:

No	Position/Division	Number of people)
1	Branch Manager	1
2	Sales	12
3	Service	14
4	Part	2
5	BackOffice	5
Total		44

Table 1: Distribution of Total Employees of PT. United Motors Center Jember Branch

The problems that have been described above also of course occur at PT.UMC Suzuki Jember Branch. Therefore researchers are trying to measure the employees who work at PT. UMC Jember branch so that the employee's performance is able to be more optimal to achieve company goals.

Based on the description above, the formulation of the problem that the author can put forward is as follows:

- Does the incentive factor, work facilities and leadership style partially affect the performance of employees at PT. UMC Jember Branch ?
- Does the incentive factor, work facilities and leadership style simultaneously affect the performance of employees at PT. UMC Jember Branch?
- Of the three factors, namely the incentive factor, work facilities and leadership style, which factor has the most dominant influence on employee performance at PT. UMC Jember Branch?

Based on the description of the background and the formulation of the problems in this study, then on this occasion the objectives of this research will be conveyed, namely:

- Want to know the factors of incentives, work facilities and leadership style partially affect the performance of employees at PT. UMC Jember Branch.
- Want to know the factors of incentives, work facilities and leadership style simultaneously affect the performance of employees at PT. UMC Jember Branch.
- Of the three factors, namely incentives, work facilities and leadership style, we want to know which has the most dominant influence on employee performance at PT. UMC Jember Branch

The hope is that the results of research conducted by researchers are able to benefit the company, especially in making a strategic decision to improve employee performance where the final output is an increase in overall company performance and an increase in company profits.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Incentive

Yuniarsih and Suwatno (2013: 131) state that incentives are awards or rewards given to motivate workers or members of the organization so that their motivation and work productivity are high, are not fixed or intermittent. Likewise, according to Handoko (2017: 176) suggests that incentives are incentives offered to employees to carry out work according to or higher than the standards that have been set. According to Irham (2017: 64), incentives are a form of remuneration given to an employee for work performance, both financial and non-financial.

According to Hasibuan (2006: 184) indicators of incentives are:

- Social Security
- Bonus
- Awards
- Promotion
- Promotion.

B. Work Facilities

In an effort to improve employee performance, it is necessary to approach it by paying attention to the psychological factors inherent in employees such as motivation, calmness, personality, emotionality and so on. Basically, employees will feel comfortable and at ease at work if work facilities are available that enable their needs to be fulfilled as human beings, not as mere means of production.

Work facilities are factors that cannot be separated from the world of work and are the most important thing for employees to complete their tasks. The availability of facilities in the form of complete work support facilities and infrastructure will encourage employees to increase their productivity. The implications that arise from these conditions are that employee performance will be more optimal and the goals of the organization can be achieved effectively and efficiently.

According to Koyong (2011: 11), work facilities are a form of company service to employees in order to support performance in meeting employee needs, so as to increase employee work productivity.

Basically the company owns and provides supporting facilities that will later function to assist the work process within the company. Adequate work facilities will of course have a positive impact on work processes within the company. Work facilities used in various forms, types and benefits are adjusted to the needs of the company or agency. Employee work facilities should be adjusted to their work so that they do not hinder work.

Facilities are the main supporting factor in a service, because what does it mean for an agency/company without facilities, without office equipment, and without manpower, maybe just a nameplate. According to Sofyan (2010:22), the types of work facilities consist of:

- Machinery and equipment which is the entire equipment used to support the production process in the company.
- Infrastructure, namely supporting facilities used to facilitate company activities, including bridges, roads, fences and others.
- Office equipment, namely facilities that support activities in the office, such as office furniture (tables, chairs, cabinets, and others). Laboratory equipment and electronic equipment (computers, copiers, printers and other calculating devices).
- Inventory equipment, namely equipment that is considered as necessary tools within the company such as vehicle inventory, office inventory, factory inventory, laboratory inventory, warehouse inventory and others.
- Land, namely assets that are spread out widely both used in building sites, as well as those used for company activities.
- Buildings, namely facilities that support the central activities of the main company activities such as offices and warehousing.
- Means of transportation, namely all equipment used to assist the implementation of company activities such as vehicles (trucks, tractors, cars, motorbikes, and others).

There are several indicators of work facilities according to (Moenir, 2016: 120), namely:

- Working tools
- Work equipment facilities
- Social facilities

C. Leadership Style

Leadership style is the essence of organizational management, basic resources, and the central point of every activity that occurs in an organization. So leadership style is a very important factor in leading and influencing organizational achievement.

Hasibuan (2012: 170) defines leadership style as the way a leader influences the behavior of subordinates, so they want to work together and work productively to achieve organizational goals. Likewise, according to Yuniarsih (2011: 165-166) Leadership style can be interpreted as a person's ability and strength to influence the

minds (mindset) of other people so that they are willing and able to follow their will, and inspire other parties to design something more meaningful.

According to Siagian (Duha, 2016: 108), said there are five types of leadership whose existence is recognized, namely:

- The Autocratic Type, The autocratic leader is a very selfish person.
- Paternalistic Type, Leader or role model
- The charismatic type, the leader who is dignified and has its own allure.
- The Laissez Feire type, a leader who plays a passive role and lets activities take their course.
- The Democratic type, a leader who listens to the opinions, suggestions and even criticism of others, especially his subordinates.

The description put forward by several experts illustrates that the right leadership style has a positive impact on organizational productivity, and vice versa with an inappropriate leadership style, organizational or company goals can be disrupted and cause employees to feel frustration, hatred, anxiety and dissatisfaction.

According to Martoyo quoted by Delti (2015:497-498), indicators of leadership style are:

- Analytical Ability
- Skills
- Courage
- Listening Ability
- Firmness

D. Performance

Performance is the result of a process that refers to and is measured over a certain period of time based on predetermined conditions or agreements (Edison, 2016: 190). According to Moeheriono (2012) Performance is a picture of the level of achievement of implementing a program of activities or policies in realizing the goals, objectives, vision and mission of the organization as outlined through the organization's strategic planning. Meanwhile, Mangkunegara (2001: 67) suggests that performance is the result of quality work. and the quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out their duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to them. So from the description of the definition presented by the expert, that performance is the result of a work process that has been agreed upon between the employee and the organization.

E. Factors Affecting Performance

According to Gibson (2004: 164) the factors that affect performance are as follows:

➤ Individual Factors

Individual factors include: abilities, skills, family background, work experience, social level and demographics of a person.

➤ Psychological Factors

Psychological factors consist of: perception, role, attitude, personality, motivation, work environment and job satisfaction.

➤ *Organizational Factors*
Organizational structure, job design, leadership and rewards.

F. Performance Indicator

There are 6 indicators for measuring employee performance individually, Bernardin, in Robbins (2006: 260), namely:

- *Quality*
Quality of work is measured by employees' perceptions of the quality of work produced and the perfection of tasks on the skills and abilities of employees.
- *Quantity*
This is the amount generated expressed in terms such as the number of units, the number of activity cycles completed.
- *Punctuality*
Is the level of activity completed at the beginning of the stated time, seen from the point of coordination with the output results and maximizing the time available for other activities.
- *Effectiveness*
Is the level of use of organizational resources (energy, money, technology, raw materials) is maximized with the intention of increasing the results of each unit in the use of resources.
- *Independence*
This is the level of an employee who will be able to carry out his work functions without asking for help, guidance from other people or supervisors.
- *Work commitment*
Is a level where employees have a commitment to work with agencies and employee responsibilities towards the office

III. HYPOTHESIS

In analyzing this research Incentives (X1), Work Facilities (X2), Leadership Style (X3) on Employee Performance (Y), the framework of thought in this study is described as follows:

Fig. 1: Thinking Framework

From the concept of the research framework, the authors make the following hypothesis:

- Incentive factors, work facilities, and leadership style partially affect the performance of employees of PT. UMC Jember Branch.
- Factors of incentives, work facilities, and leadership style simultaneously affect the performance of employees of PT. UMC Jember Branch
- Of the three factors, namely, the incentive factor, work facilities, and leadership style, the incentive factor is the most dominant factor affecting the performance of employees of PT. UMC Jember Branch.

IV. RESEARCH METHODS

A. Time and place

The research location is located at PT. United Motors Center (UMC) Jember Branch, Jl. Hayam Wuruk no. 2 kaliwates, Kec. Kaliwates, Kab. Jember , East Java 68131 Tel (0331) 424875

The time that will be used to conduct this research is approximately three months starting from October to December 2022.

B. Population and Sample

According to Sugiyono (2018: 72) Population is a generalization area consisting of: objects/subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by researchers to study and then draw conclusions. The population in this study were all employees of PT.UMC Jember Branch with a total of 44 people working at PT. UMC Jember Branch.

Then also according to Sugiyono (2018: 73) the sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population. If the population is large and it is impossible for the researcher to study everything in the population, for example due to limited funds, manpower and time, the researcher can use samples taken from that population.

With a population of up to 2022 the number of company employees is 44 people, the determination of the research sample uses a saturated sample. Saturated Sample is a sampling technique when all members of the population are used as samples (Sugiyono, 2018: 68). According to Arikunto (2017: 173) says that if the subject is less than 100, then the entire population becomes the research sample, thus the entire population in this study is used as a sample. Thus it can be concluded that the sample is the object studied from the total population with the condition that the subject is less than 100. Determining the number of samples taken in this study is the total population of 44 people.

C. Identification and Definition of Operational Variables

➤ Variable Identification

In relation to this research, the state of the method is considered a good guideline or basis, in this case data collection and data analysis so that it will provide good direction.

- Independent variable (independent variable)
 - ✓ Incentive
 - ✓ Work Facilities
 - ✓ Leadership
- Dependent variable (dependent variable)
- Employee performance

➤ Variable Operational Definitions

Operational definition is a definition given to a variable by giving meaning, specifying activities, or providing an operation needed to measure that variable. Then the definition of the variable used is:

- Independent Variable (X1) Incentives
 - ✓ Social Security
 - ✓ Bonus
 - ✓ Awards
 - ✓ Promotion
 - ✓ Promotion
- Independent Variable (X2) Work Facilities
 - ✓ Working tools
 - ✓ Work equipment facilities
 - ✓ Social facilities
- Independent Variable (X3) Leadership style
 - ✓ Analytical Ability
 - ✓ Skills
 - ✓ Courage
 - ✓ Listening Ability
- Dependent Variable (Y) Employee Performance
 - ✓ Quality .
 - ✓ quantity .
 - ✓ Punctuality .
 - ✓ Effectiveness .
 - ✓ independence
 - ✓ work commitment

➤ Data collection technique

Data collection techniques in this study were carried out in the following way:

- Observation.
- Interview
- Questionnaire
- Documentation

D. Data Analysis Method

➤ Validity test

Validity Test is a measure that shows the levels of validity of an instrument according to Arikunto (2017:14)

The method is to connect or correlate between the scores obtained on each question item and the total individual score. Testing the validity of each question item is done by calculating the Pearson product moment correlation between the item scores and the total score. A question item is said to be valid if the significance is < 0.05 .

The correlation value between the data in each statement and the total score is calculated using the product moment correlation technical formula, namely calculating the correlation between each question and the total score using the following formula, (Suharsimi Arikunto, 2005; 146):

$$r = \frac{n(\sum xy) - (\sum x \sum y)}{\sqrt{[n \sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2][n \sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2]}}$$

Where :

r = Correlation between x and y

x = Score of each question item

y = Total score

n = Number of respondents

➤ Reliability Test

Reliability is carried out to measure the consistency of constructs or research variables of a questionnaire said to be reliable or reliable if a person's answers to the questions are consistent or stable from time to time. To measure reliability with the Cronbach Alpha Statistical Test, a variable is said to be reliable if it has a Cronbach Alpha value > 0.600 . Cronbach Alpha technique using the coefficient (α), (Suharsimi Arikunto, 2005; 146) with a mathematical formula is:

$$r = \left(\frac{k}{k-1} \right) \left(1 - \frac{\sum \alpha b^2}{\alpha t^2} \right)$$

Where :

r = Instrument reliability

k = The number of questions

$\sum \alpha b^2$ = Total variety

αt^2 = The number of various items

➤ Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Multiple linear regression analysis is needed to determine the regression coefficients and their significance so that they can be used to answer the hypothesis.

In general, the formulation of multiple regression can be written as follows: (J. Supranto, 2002; 207)

$$Y = +1X_1 + 2X_2 + 3X_3 + e \alpha \beta \beta$$

Information:

Y = Employee Performance

α = Intercept/constant value

X₁ = Incentive Variable

X₂ = Work Facility Variable

X₃ = Leadership Style Variable

$\beta_1, 2, 3$ = Regression coefficient of independent variables $\beta \beta$

e = standard error (error rate)

➤ t test (t Test)

To test the variables that have an effect on between X₁, X₂, X₃ on Y individually (partially) then the t test is used. According to Sugiyono (2018: 214) the formula for calculating the t test is as follows:

$$t = \frac{b}{Sb}$$

Where:

t = t count

b = regression coefficient

Sb = standard deviation of the independent variables

With acceptance criteria:

- If t count > t table, then Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted, which means that there is a significant influence between the independent variables on the dependent variable.
- If t count < t table, then Ho is accepted and Ha is rejected, which means that there is no significant effect between the independent variables on the dependent variable.
- significant level (α) = 0.05 ; t table = n - k - 1

Where :

n = Samples

k = Independent Variable

➤ *F Test (F Test)*

To test the variables that have an effect on between X1, X2, X3 on Y simultaneously (simultaneously), the F test is used.

This F test is also called a simultaneous test or jointly affects Y, namely to test the variables that have an intermediate effect X_1, X_2 simultaneously (simultaneously) to Y with the following formula: (Sugiyono, 2018:257)

$$F = \frac{R^2(n - K - 1)}{K(1 - R^2)}$$

Information :

R = Determinant coefficient

K = Lots of free change

n = Number of data

The hypothesis to be used with real distances $\alpha = 0,05$ that is :

Ho : $\beta \leq 0 \Rightarrow$ Ho accepted (H_1 rejected) means that there is no positive and significant influence between the independent variables incentives, work facilities, and leadership style.

$H_1 : \beta \geq 0 \Rightarrow$ Ho is rejected (H_1 accepted) means that there is a positive and significant influence between incentives, work facilities, and leadership style.

- If the probability $F > 0.05$ then Ho is accepted H_1 rejected.
- If the probability $F < 0.05$ then Ho is rejected H_1 accepted.

F table = (n - k ; k - 1)

Where :

n = Samples

k = independent variable

➤ *Coefficient of Determination*

The coefficient of determination is used to show how much influence the two variables studied, then the coefficient of determination (Kd) with other factors outside the variables considered constant / fixed (ceteris paribus). The formula for the coefficient of determination (Kd) is:(Ghozali, 2005:83)

$$kd = r^2 \times 100\%$$

Information:

Kd = Coefficient of Determination

R = Correlation Coefficient

Where if:

Kd = 0, means that the effect of variable X on variable Y is weak.

Kd = 1, means that the influence of variable X on variable Y is strong.

The influence of the high and low coefficient of determination is used by the guidelines proposed by Guiford quoted by Supranto (2001: 227) as follows:

No	Coefficient Intervals	Relationship Level
1	0.80 – 1.000	Very strong
2	0.60 – 0.799	Strong
3	0.40 – 0.599	Strong enough
4	0.20 – 0.399	Low
5	0.00 – 0.199	Very low

Table 2: High Low Coefficient of Determination

Source: Riduwan and Kuncoro (2017:62)

V. RESEARCH RESULTS

A. Validity test

Validity test is a measure that shows the levels of validity and validity of an instrument. An instrument is said to be valid if it is able to measure what it wants to measure or can disclose data from the variables studied appropriately. The level of instrument validity indicates the extent to which the data collected does not deviate from the description of the variable in question. The results of the validity test can be described as follows:

Indicator	r Count	r Table	Information
Social Games(X1.1)	0.429	0.297	Valid
Bonus(X1.2)	0.861	0.297	Valid
Awards(X1.3)	0.929	0.297	Valid
Promotion(X1.4)	0.926	0.297	Valid
Promotion(X1.5)	0.791	0.297	Valid
Working Tool Facilities(X2.1)	0.906	0.297	Valid
Work Equipment Facilities(X2.2)	0.910	0.297	Valid
Social Facilities(X2.3)	0.897	0.297	Valid
Analytical Ability(X3.1)	0.937	0.297	Valid
Skills(X3.2)	0.986	0.297	Valid
Courage(X3.3)	0.902	0.297	Valid
Listening Ability(X3.4)	0.968	0.297	Valid
Quality(Y1.1)	0.878	0.297	Valid
Quantity(Y1.2)	0.857	0.297	Valid
Punctuality(Y1.3)	0.853	0.297	Valid
effectiveness(Y1.4)	0.787	0.297	Valid
independence(Y1.5)	0.805	0.297	Valid
Work Commitment(Y1.6)	0.625	0.297	Valid

Table 3: Validity Test Results

From table 3 above it can be seen that the validity coefficient value of each question item is greater than the r table of 0.297 with an error rate of 5% ($\alpha = 0.05$) which means that each variable item is valid, so it can be concluded that these items can be used to measure incentives, work facilities, leadership style and employee performance variables.

B. Reliability Test

The reliability testing technique is to use the alpha reliability coefficient value. The decision making criterion is if the value of the reliability coefficient alpha is greater than 0.6 then the variable is reliable. The results of the reliability test can be presented in the following table:

Category	Mark	Cronbach's Alpha	Information
Incentive (X1)	0.885	0.60	Reliable
Work Facilities (X2)	0.918	0.60	Reliable
Leadership Style (X3)	0.976	0.60	Reliable
Employee Performance (Y)	0.916	0.60	Reliable

Table 4: Recapitulation of Reliability Test Results

From table 4 above it can be seen that the reliability test is to test from a measuring instrument for each variable. Shows that all variables have a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient that is greater than 0.60. Thus it can be concluded that all measuring concepts for each variable are reliable.

C. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Regression analysis was carried out to prove the hypothesis proposed in this study, namely to analyze the effect of the independent variables (Incentives, Work Facilities and Leadership Style) on Employee Performance, both partially and simultaneously as well as to test the research hypotheses that have been stated previously. For more details, it can be seen through the following table:

Coefficientsa

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	std. Error	Betas			tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	-1.951E-16	.096		,000	1,000		
INCENTIVE	,382	,157	,382	2,437	,019	,383	2,614
WORK FACILITIES	,366	,154	,366	2,381	,022	,398	2,515
LEADERSHIP STYLE	,279	,125	,279	2,204	,036	,851	1,176

Table 5: Recapitulation of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Results

a. Dependent Variable: EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE

Based on Table 5, the multiple linear regression equation can be obtained as follows:

$$Y = -1.951E-16 + 0.382X_1 + 0.366X_2 + 0.279X_3 + e$$

Information :

Y = dependent variable, namely employee performance

X1 = Independent variable, namely incentives

X2 = Independent variable, namely work facilities

X3 = Independent variable, namely Leadership Style

The results of the linear regression equation above show that:

- Constant value = -1.951E-16 this shows that if the independent variables (X1, X2 and X3) are assumed to be constant, then the forecast value on employee performance (Y) is
- b1 = 0.382 is the coefficient of the regression variable Incentives. meaning that if the incentive variable increases by one unit, employee performance will

increase by 0.382 assuming the Work Facilities and Leadership Style variables are constant.

- b2 = 0.366 is the regression coefficient of the work facilities variable, meaning that if the work facilities variable increases by one unit, employee performance will increase by 0.366 assuming constant incentives and leadership style.
- b3 = 0.279 is the coefficient of the leadership style variable, meaning that if the leadership style variable increases by one unit, employee performance will increase by 0.279 assuming the Incentives and Work Facilities variables are constant.
- e = 0.096 the residual value/possible error of the regression equation model due to the possibility of other variables that can affect the variable Employee performance(Y) but not included in the equation model. The standard error is 0.096, meaning that all variables calculated in the SPSS version 22 test for Windows 7 have a confounding variable level of 0.096.

D. Coefficient of Determination (R²)

The coefficient of determination is used to show how much influence the three variables are examined, so the coefficient of determination (Kd) is calculated with other factors outside the variables considered constant / fixed (cateris paribus).

➤ *Summary modelb*

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	,790a	,624	,596	,63544699	2,606

Table 6: Determination Coefficient Test Results (R²)

- a. Predictors: (Constant), LEADERSHIP STYLE, WORK FACILITIES, INCENTIVES
- b. Dependent Variable: EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE

The results of the analysis of the influence of incentives (X1), work facilities (X2), and leadership style (X3) on employee performance (Y) as in the table above, shows the value of the coefficient of determination or Rsquare shows a value of 0.624, from these results it means that all independent variables (Incentives, work facilities and leadership style) has a contribution of 62.4% to the dependent variable (employee performance) with a high or strong influence, and the remaining 37.6% is influenced by other factors not included in the study.

E. Hypothesis Testing Results

➤ *T test results (t-test)*

This test is intended to determine the effect of each independent variable on the dependent variable by comparing the calculated t value with ttable, with a degree of freedom of 95% (α = 5%) with testing criteria:

- If t count > t table: H0 is rejected and Ha is accepted
- If t count < t table: H0 is accepted and Ha is rejected

Coefficientsa

Model			Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	std. Error	Betas		
1 (Constant)	-1.951E-16	.096		,000	1,000
INCENTIVE	,382	,157	,382	2,437	,019
WORK FACILITIES	,366	,154	,366	2,381	,022
LEADERSHIP STYLE	,279	,125	,279	2,204	,036

Table 7: Recapitulation of Test Results t

- a. Dependent Variable: EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE

Based on the results of partial testing regarding the effect of each variable, it can be described as follows:

- The effect of the incentive variable (X1) on employee performance (Y) shows that the value of $t_{count} > t_{table}$ is $2.437 > 2.021$, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This means that the Incentive variable (X1) partially has a significant effect on employee performance (Y) at PT. United Motors Center Jember Branch.
- The effect of the variable work facilities (X2) on employee performance (Y) shows that $t_{count} > t_{table}$, namely $2.381 > 2.021$, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. It means that the work facility variable (X2) partially has a significant effect on employee performance (Y) at PT. United Motors Center Jember Branch.
- The influence of the leadership style variable (X3) on employee performance (Y) shows that $t_{count} > t_{table}$, namely $2.204 > 2.021$, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is

accepted. It means that the leadership style variable (X3) partially has a significant effect on employee performance (Y) at PT. United Motors Center Jember Branch.

➤ *F Test Results (F-test)*

The calculated F test is carried out to see simultaneously or together how the influence of the independent variable (X) has on the dependent variable (Y). The F test formula that is in The F test formula quoted from (Sugiyono, 2016: 192) are as follows:

Simultaneously incentives, work facilities and leadership style have a significant effect on employee performance, which is indicated by statistical testing through the F test which can be seen through the following table.

ANOVAa						
	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	26,848	3	8,949	22,163	,000b
	residual	16.152	40	,404		
	Total	43,000	43			

Table 8: F test recapitulation

a. Dependent Variable: EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE

b. Predictors: (Constant), LEADERSHIP STYLE, WORK FACILITIES, INCENTIVES

• Define F_{table}

If using a 95% confidence level or $\alpha = 5\%$, df_1 can be determined by the following equation:

$$df_1 = k - 1 ; \text{ means } df_1 = 3 ; (4 - 1)$$

$$df_2 = n - k ; \text{ means } df_2 = 40 ; (44 - 4)$$

• Comparing F_{count} with F_{table}

$$F_{count} > F_{table} (22.163 > 2.84)$$

Theoretically, incentives, work facilities and leadership styles have a significant influence on employee performance. Comparison between F_{table} and F_{count} where F_{count} is $22.163 > F_{table} 2.84$, it can be concluded that incentives, work facilities and leadership style have a significant influence on employee performance. So it can be concluded that based on theory and statistical results of research based on the F test, incentives, work facilities and leadership style have a simultaneous influence on the performance of employees of PT. United Motors Center Jember Branch.

F. Simultaneous Hypothesis Testing Dominance Test

Based on theoretical explanations and statistical results from the study, it can be concluded that the effect of the Incentive variable (X1) on employee performance (Y) indicates that the $t_{count} > t_{table}$ is $2.437 > 2.021$, so H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This means that the Incentive variable (X1) partially has a significant effect on employee performance (Y) at PT. United Motors Center Jember Branch.

Work facilities variable (X2) on employee performance (Y) shows that $t_{count} > t_{table}$ is $2.381 > 2.021$ then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. It means that the work facility variable (X2) partially has a significant effect on employee performance (Y) at PT. United Motors Center Jember Branch.

Leadership style variable (X3) on employee performance (Y) shows that $t_{count} > t_{table}$, namely $2.204 > 2.021$, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. It means that the leadership style variable (X3) partially has a significant effect on employee performance (Y) at PT. United Motors Center Jember Branch.

In this study, it turns out that the incentive variable has the most dominant influence on employee performance at PT. United Motors Center Jember Branch, further influenced by work facilities and leadership style.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

A. Conclusion

Based on the descriptions that have been disclosed in the discussion, several conclusions can be drawn as answers to the main issues raised in this study, namely:

- The results of the t test results of partial testing regarding the influence of each variable Incentives, Work Facilities, and Leadership Style can be described as follows:
- ✓ Variable influence Incentives (X1) on employee performance (Y) show that the value of $t_{count} > t_{table}$ is $2.437 > 2.021$, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This means that the Incentive variable (X1) partially has

a significant effect on employee performance (Y) at PT. United Motors Center Jember Branch.

- ✓ The effect of the variable work facilities (X2) on employee performance (Y) shows that $t_{count} > t_{table}$, namely $2.381 > 2.021$, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. It means that the work facility variable (X2) partially has a significant effect on employee performance (Y) at PT. United Motors Center Jember Branch.
- ✓ The influence of the leadership style variable (X3) on employee performance (Y) shows that $t_{count} > t_{table}$, namely $2.204 > 2.021$, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. It means that the leadership style variable (X3) partially has a significant effect on employee performance (Y) at PT. United Motors Center Jember Branch.
- ✓ Theoretically, incentives, work facilities and leadership styles have a significant influence on employee performance. Comparison between F_{table} and F_{count} where F_{count} is $22.163 > F_{table} 2.84$, it can be concluded that incentives, work facilities and leadership style have a significant influence on employee performance. So it can be concluded that based on theory and statistical results of research based on the F test, incentives, work facilities and leadership style have a simultaneous influence on the performance of employees of PT. United Motors Center Jember Branch
- Simultaneous Hypothesis Testing Dominance Test Based on the theoretical explanation and statistical results from the study, it can be concluded that Incentives (X1) on employee performance (Y) show that the value of $t_{count} > t_{table}$ is $2.437 > 2.021$, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This means that the Incentive variable (X1) partially has a significant effect on employee performance (Y) at PT. United Motors Center Jember Branch. Work facilities variable (X2) on employee performance (Y) shows that $t_{count} > t_{table}$, namely $2.381 > 2.021$, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. It means that the work facility variable (X2) partially has a significant effect on employee performance (Y) at PT. United Motors Center Jember Branch.

Leadership style variable (X3) on employee performance (Y) shows that $t_{count} > t_{table}$, namely $2.204 > 2.021$, then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. It means that the leadership style variable (X3) partially has a significant effect on employee performance (Y) at PT. United Motors Center Jember Branch. In this study, it turns out that the incentive variable has the most dominant influence on employee performance at PT. United Motors Center Jember Branch, further influenced by work facilities and leadership style.

- The results of the analysis of the influence of incentives (X1), work facilities (X2), and leadership style (X3) on employee performance (Y) as in the table above, shows the value of the coefficient of determination or R^2 shows a value of 0.624, from these results it means that all independent variables (Incentives, work facilities and leadership style) has a contribution of 62.4% to the dependent variable (employee performance) with a high

or strong influence, and the remaining 37.6% is influenced by other factors not included in the study.

B. Suggestion

Based on the results of the discussion and conclusions the authors provide several suggestions, including:

- Based on this research, the Incentive Variable has a dominant level of influence on employee performance, this needs to be maintained by the Leaders PT. United Motors Center Jember Branch so that employees maintain the quality of their performance.
- Work facilities in PT. United Motors Center Jember Branch currently it is good but still needs to be improved, and coupled with better facilities and already following existing technology, this is so that employee performance can increase and be useful for getting high quality as well as work productivity.
- The leadership style applied to employees of PT. United Motors Center needs to pay more attention, in this case leaders need to improve their ability to analyze work, skills in completing work, courage in making decisions, and listening to employee complaints so that they can influence employee performance.
- For researchers who are interested in conducting research on incentives, work facilities and leadership style in the future, it is advisable to expand more on the variables, indicators, area of study, and types of research objects.
- The research results should be used as material for further research taking into account the limitations of this study.

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